

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 21.10.2020 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Prof. Devaseelan S	Chairman,
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
4. Ms. Oshin Mathew	Member
5. Ms. Varsha A C	Member
6. Ms. Shaik Farheen	Member
7. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
8. Mrs. Laveena D'Souza	Member
9. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
10. Mr. Jibin Simon	Member
11. Mrs. Bhavya R Nayak	Member
12. Mrs. Priyadhersini. S	Member
13. Dr. Sohan Rodney Bangera	Member

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 12.06.2020.
2. Proposed a plan to add external members and Industrial Expert to BOS
3. Discussion about existing Syllabus
4. Online Class Confirmation

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 12.06.2020. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Science Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: A proposal was made to add the External members to the Board of Studies. The suggestion was made so as to enable improvements in the syllabus of the courses. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members to add the External Members to the Board of Studies.

Agenda No. 3: The Chairperson proposed a discussion regarding the existing syllabus and suggestion was given to update the current syllabus of every courses according to the existing demand. The resolution was taken as per the suggestions of BOS Members and all the courses were asked to give an update regarding the same in the next meeting.

Agenda No. 4: The Chairperson stated the need of online classes and to keep curriculum coverage as most preferred task. The discussion was made regarding the pros and cons of online classes. It was decided to check on the new possibilities or options for the improvement in the online classes. Resolution was taken accordingly as per the suggestion proposed by the Chairperson and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Varsha A C, Member of Board of Studies.

Prof. Devaseelan S,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Members present:

Prof. Devaseelan S

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Mrs. Swathi D

Ms. Oshin Mathew

Ms. Shaik Farheen

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